

Understanding Colour Theory and Practical Application across Cross-Disciplinary Borders: Effective Pedagogical Strategy for Teaching Graphics, Painting, and Printmaking

¹AKHOGBA, Albert Ehi, ²GANDONU Sewanu Peter

Corresponding author: gandonusp@lasued.edu.ng

¹Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma Edo State

²Lagos State University of Education, Oto/Ijanikin Lagos State

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19286628>

Abstract

Understanding the characteristics of colour; and experiencing its practical use is fundamental to visual communication in various colour-dependent art specializations. These include printmaking, painting, and graphics. However, transforming theoretical colour principles into useful studio outcomes can be challenging for students. This study covers instructional approaches for bridging the gap between theoretical comprehension and real-world application of colour knowledge across these three areas of visual art specialization. The study uses a qualitative methodology to examine studio practices, instructional strategies, and student experiences. It reveals that learners' capacity to engage with colour in a variety of scenarios can be better improved by studio-based practical learnings, cross-disciplinary studio workshops, digital resources, and reflective critique sessions. In artistic fields such as graphics, painting and printing, colour understanding is central to art practice and visual communication. The study suggests a model for comprehensive colour education in schools by concluding that cross-disciplinary teaching with both analog and digital resources will promote deeper understanding and creative confidence of the students in colour application.

Keywords: Colour, graphics, pedagogical strategies, practical applications, painting

Introduction

One of the most powerful vehicles of visual language in art is colour. It has to do with perception, emotion, and communication through different artistic mediums. Colour comprehension and handling are central creative aptitudes in the studio-based specializations; especially in graphics, painting and printmaking. However, regardless of its extensive use in art creation, many art students in these specializations exhibit little understanding of colour theory and struggle with transformation of theoretical knowledge into valuable practical outcomes (Velayutham & Raman, 2024). The segmented instruction in which colour theory is usually imparted as a stand-alone theoretical subject without corresponding studio procedures and relative practical application, could be the basis of this separation. The main concern in this situation is that students may understand colour relationships as they learnt them in the theories, yet lack the necessary practical experience required to apply them successfully in their art creations (Baper, Husein, & Salim, 2021).

Against this background, the objective of this study is to cross-examine instructional methods in art, and how they support students to effectively transform theoretical colour knowledge into practical outcomes in graphics, painting, and printmaking. The study explores how interdisciplinary studio experiences stimulate creative improvement and further students' application of common knowledge of colour principles. Woon Lam (2018) observes that despite the importance of colour in visual arts, many students find it difficult to transform theoretical ideas to real-life art production. The disparities in how colour is applied in printmaking, graphics, and painting studios underscores the need for critical aspects of colour, to be taught and learnt in both theory and practice. The compartmentalization of art programs in Universities limits students' critical thinking abilities and collaborative experiences across the borders of colour-related specializations. This also aggravates the concern.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Reflexive Practice: Donald Schön (1983)

Donald Schön promoted the Theory of Reflexive Praxis, also known as Reflexive Practice, in 1983. It is a critical self-evaluation that involves continually evaluating and challenging one's own performances, presuppositions, and philosophies in order to improve performance and outcomes.

According to Reich (2017), reflexive practice also applies to experts trying to understand design better. When the way an individual's subjectivity, predispositions, and social perspective affect their creativity is analyzed, it results in more well-informed and effective practice, than simple reflection. It comprises both adapting to circumstances as they arise and applying lessons from the past to advance upcoming actions. This perspective places a strong emphasis on learning through reflection on experience, or reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action, as held by Donald Schön. Though, reflection in art production comprises literal and figurative interpretations, its instruction usually includes both theoretical contents and studio-practice. When focus is placed on dialogic relationships in art-practice, "reflexive praxis" improves both individual and group educational experiences.

This study engages the perspective of Reflexive Praxis to examine ways in which art educators and students reflect on the complications and outcomes of applying colour theory to the practical demands in printmaking graphics and painting. This will help in bridging the gap between art students' theoretical understanding of colour and the medium's characteristics, as well as its effective application for valuable art creation.

The Context: Colour

Colour is one of the most fundamental and expressive elements of visual art, functioning simultaneously as a physical phenomenon, a psychological stimulus, and a powerful cultural signifier (Zihan, 2025). At its most basic level, colour emerges from light and human perception, yet within artistic practice it transcends scientific explanation to become a language through which meaning, emotion, and identity are communicated. According to Pan, Pan and Zhang (2024), artists and art students deploy colour not merely to describe form or surface, but to evoke mood, direct attention, establish harmony or tension, and construct visual narratives that resonate with viewers across time and space.

In visual composition, colour operates structurally and symbolically. Structurally, it organizes pictorial space, creates emphasis, and establishes relationships between forms. Warm colours such as red, orange, and yellow tend to advance visually, generating energy and immediacy, while cool colours such as blue and green often recede, producing calmness and spatial depth. Through contrasts of hue, value, and saturation, artists achieve balance, rhythm, and movement within a composition. Colour

harmony can unify disparate elements, while deliberate dissonance can provoke discomfort, urgency, or critical reflection (Weingerl & Javoršek, 2018). Beyond formal considerations, colour exerts a profound psychological influence. Human responses to colour are often intuitive and emotional, shaped by both biological perception and learned experience. Prachi and Vaibhav, (2025) explain that colours can stimulate excitement, tranquility, fear, or nostalgia, making them potent tools for emotional communication in painting, design, advertising, and digital media. Artists and students of art consciously manipulate colour to shape perception, influence behaviour, and construct meaning, underscoring its relevance not only in fine art but also in interdisciplinary fields such as psychology, marketing, and visual communication.

Colour also functions as a carrier of cultural meaning. Across societies, colours are embedded with symbolic values that reflect historical experience, religious belief, and social conventions. In many African contexts, including Nigeria, colour is deeply rooted in indigenous aesthetics, ritual practices, textiles, body adornment, and architectural decoration. Colours such as white, red, indigo, and earth tones often convey spiritual, political, or communal significance, transforming visual expression into a site of cultural continuity and resistance (Zihan, 2025). According to the source, contemporary artists frequently draw upon these colour traditions, recontextualizing them within modern and globalized visual languages.

In the context of globalization and contemporary visual art education, colour assumes renewed significance. Digital technologies have expanded the possibilities of colour production, manipulation, and dissemination, introducing new chromatic experiences through screens, software, and multimedia platforms. This shift demands a rethinking of how colour is taught and understood, moving beyond traditional pigment-based instruction to include digital colour theory, cross-cultural interpretation, and interdisciplinary application. Colour literacy thus becomes essential for preparing artists to engage effectively within global creative industries.

Colour therefore, is not a decorative afterthought but a central force in visual meaning-making. Its ability to bridge emotion, culture, perception, and communication positions it as a vital element in both artistic practice and visual art education. A critical and contextual understanding of colour enables

artists and students to engage more deeply with their work, articulate complex ideas, and contribute meaningfully to cultural and economic discourse in an increasingly interconnected world

Colour Theory and its Pedagogical Foundations

From ancient times to the present, colour theory has a long history and comprises academic and systematic studies of ways in which colour is perceived and comprehended by individuals (Cianci, 2023). According to Cole (2025), it also covers valuable practices of colour use in artistic activities. In art and design education, colour theory is an essential framework that helps students comprehend the emotional and visual impacts of colour. It also provides a systematic approach to how colours interact, harmonize, and express meaning in visual compositions. According to Adejumo (2015), early philosophers like Aristotle, Leonardo da Vinci, and Isaac Newton are credited with laying the groundwork for contemporary colour systems through their observations of light and the spectrum. Through studies and practices of relating colour correlations to perception, psychology, and expression, artists and educators such as Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, Johannes Itten, and Josef Albers developed this concept over time (Mitchell, 2025).

In terms of pedagogy, teaching colour theory requires a studio-based, experiential approach. Students must actively participate in pigment mixing, media experimentation, and colour changes under various lighting conditions (Eisner, 2002). They understand abstract ideas in real-world contexts through this kind of experiential learning. Constructivist learning theories, which emphasize learning through doing, discovery, and reflection, are consistent with this method. Therefore, it is the educators' responsibility to direct inquiry, promote critical discussion about colour choices, and support students' individual interpretation. Pitre (2025) also emphasizes how teaching colour theory fosters interdisciplinary thinking. Similarly, Serón, Sanz, Rodriguez-Casals, Terrado Sieso, Pozuelo Muñoz and Cascarosa (2025) also emphasize that it connects art with science, such as understanding light and optics, psychology, such as in exploring colour perception, emotion, and culture, relating to interpreting symbolic meanings of colour in various societies. In a contemporary setting, digital technology has further expanded the pedagogical scope, allowing students to experiment with virtual colour palettes, digital design tools, and augmented reality applications that simulate real-world visual effects.

Bridging Theory and Practice in Art Education

Art education thrives on the dynamic interaction between theory and practice. Theory provides the intellectual framework that shapes how art is understood, interpreted, and taught, while practice involves the hands-on processes of creating, experimenting, and expressing through visual forms (Tyrrell, 2025). Tola, Tadesse, Admassu and Alemayehu (2025) also assert that bridging these two elements ensures that learners not only acquire technical skills but also develop critical, reflective, and conceptual understanding of their artistic expressions.

In many educational settings, theory and practice are often treated as separate entities, one limited to the classroom through lectures and readings, and the other restricted to the studio through practical exercises. However, Arohunmolase (2025) asserts that a true art education experience demands their integration. The source further explains that when theory informs practice, it gives meaning and direction to creative work; when practice reinforces theory, it transforms abstract ideas into tangible experiences. This reciprocal relationship nurtures well-rounded artists and educators who can think deeply and create with purpose. For instance, theoretical knowledge about art movements, aesthetics, and cultural contexts enables students to situate their work within broader artistic traditions and contemporary issues. Reynolds (2023) expatiates that understanding concepts like symbolism, semiotics, or visual communication can help students make deliberate choices in composition, colour, and form. On the other hand, the act of creating, mixing colours, sculpting forms, or experimenting with digital media, allows learners to test and reinterpret theoretical ideas, leading to personal discovery and innovation.

Pedagogically, bridging theory and practice requires experiential and reflective teaching methods. Educators must design learning environments that encourage dialogue between thinking and doing. According to Ryan, Morel, Goodman, Hermes, Abdur Rehman, Louche and Juntunen (2025), studio critiques, reflective journals, project-based learning, and collaborative workshops all serve as effective strategies to help students connect conceptual understanding with creative execution. In such spaces, mistakes become opportunities for critical learning, and artistic exploration becomes a means of knowledge construction. Moreover, technology and interdisciplinary approaches have expanded the possibilities for connecting theory and practice in art education (Amwiine & Nnenna, 2024). Digital

tools allow students to explore virtual design, animation, and interactive art, blending theoretical principles of design, communication, and audience engagement with modern creative practice. Similarly, integrating art with science, history, or social studies encourages learners to apply theoretical perspectives from multiple disciplines to their artistic processes.

Thus, bridging theory and practice in art education fosters holistic learning that combines the mind, hand, and heart. It empowers students to move beyond mere skill acquisition toward thoughtful, intentional creation. By uniting intellectual inquiry with artistic exploration, art educators prepare learners to engage critically with the world, express ideas meaningfully, and contribute innovatively to the evolving landscape of visual culture.

Colour across Disciplines

Colour is a universal language that transcends artistic boundaries and finds relevance across numerous fields of study. According to Amarjeet and Kapil (2023), while often associated with art and design, colour extends its influence into science, psychology, culture, technology, and communication. Elliot (2015) also explicates that its interdisciplinary nature demonstrates how something as simple as hue and tone can affect perception, behavior, and meaning across diverse contexts. In the visual arts, colour serves as a fundamental element of composition, emotion, and expression. Artists use colour to evoke mood, create contrast, establish harmony, and convey symbolic meaning. For example, warm colours such as red and yellow often express energy or passion, while cool tones like blue and green suggest calmness and balance (Novak, 2025). Theoretical frameworks developed by figures like Johannes Itten and Josef Albers have provided artists and designers with tools to understand colour interactions and their perceptual effects.

In science, particularly in physics and chemistry, colour is studied in terms of light waves, pigments, and the human visual system. Topper's (1990) narrative on colour explains that Isaac Newton's discovery of the colour spectrum through light refraction established the foundation for modern colour science. In biology, the study of colour relates to animal adaptation, camouflage, and signaling, while in medicine, colour perception is linked to vision health and neurological function (Duarte, Flores, & Stevens, 2017). Psychology also draws heavily on colour studies to understand human emotion and behavior. Colour psychology explores how certain hues can influence mood, productivity, and

decision-making. For instance, blue is often associated with calmness and trust, making it a common choice in corporate branding, while red may evoke excitement or urgency, often used in marketing and advertising to attract attention. In cultural studies and anthropology, colour carries deep symbolic meanings that vary across societies. White, for example, may signify purity in Western contexts but mourning in some Asian traditions. These cultural associations demonstrate how colour functions as a social code, shaping identity, ritual, and communication.

Technology and digital media have further expanded the scope of colour across disciplines. In digital design, colour theory informs user experience, accessibility, and visual hierarchy. The Red, Green, Blue (RGB) and Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, Black (CMYK) models are critical to producing accurate digital and print visuals (Adeyanju, 2020). Moreover, in fields such as fashion, architecture, and interior design, colour trends influence consumer behavior, brand identity, and spatial atmosphere. In essence, colour operates as a bridge between disciplines, a shared element that connects scientific principles, psychological experiences, and artistic expression. According to Cianci (2023), its study reveals the interdependence of perception, emotion, and culture, reminding us that colour is not merely a visual phenomenon but a complex system of communication that shapes how humans interpret and engage with the world. While painting focuses on expressive and emotional colour use, graphics prioritizes legibility, contrast, and digital calibration, and printmaking emphasizes tonal values and layered inking. A robust colour education should, therefore, incorporate the unique yet interconnected needs of these disciplines. Cross-disciplinary teaching in this sense, encourages flexibility and innovation in colour perception and application.

Technological Mediation in Colour Education

Technological mediation in colour education refers to the use of digital tools, software, and interactive media to teach and explore the principles of colour. As art and design education evolve in the digital age, technology has become a vital bridge that connects traditional colour theory with contemporary practices. It enables learners to experiment with colour relationships, simulate environments, and visualize outcomes that were once limited to physical media (Zhihui, Baoqiang, Huihui, Lin, & Li, 2024). In traditional art classrooms, colour education relied heavily on pigment mixing, painting exercises, and manual observation of light and shadow. While these methods remain essential for

understanding tactile and sensory aspects of colour, digital technologies have introduced new dimensions of learning. Software such as Adobe Photoshop, Illustrator, CorelDRAW, and Procreate allows students to manipulate digital palettes, adjust saturation and contrast, and instantly observe the impact of colour choices. These platforms also expose learners to the RGB and CMYK colour models, broadening their understanding of how colours function differently in digital and print media.

Technological mediation can therefore be seen to enhance both the accessibility and interactivity of colour education. Online simulations, virtual studios, and augmented reality applications also allow students to experiment with colour in immersive environments. For instance, digital tools can simulate how colours appear under various lighting conditions or how they influence perception in interior or fashion design. Such interactive experiences deepen students' understanding of colour harmony, temperature, and symbolism, aligning with experiential and constructivist learning theories. Furthermore, technology supports collaborative learning and global exchange of ideas (Winikoff, 2025). Through digital platforms, students can share their projects, receive instant feedback, and study diverse cultural applications of colour. This global perspective enriches their creative thinking and helps them appreciate the sociocultural dimensions of colour use across contexts.

From a pedagogical standpoint, technological mediation also empowers educators. It offers flexible instructional resources such as multimedia presentations, video tutorials, and digital colour wheels, making lessons more engaging and adaptable. According to Zhihui, et. al., (2024), teachers can integrate visual analytics and gamified learning tools to assess students' grasp of colour relationships and creative application. However, it is important to balance digital exploration with hands-on practice. Kuş (2025) warned that over-reliance on technology may limit students' tactile engagement and understanding of material colour properties such as texture, opacity, and pigment behaviour. Hence, the most effective approach combines digital experimentation with traditional studio exercises to provide a holistic learning experience.

From the foregoing, technological mediation in colour education has transformed how learners perceive, apply, and communicate through colour (Bedir & Freedman, 2024). This fusion nurtures creativity, critical thinking, and digital fluency, which are essential skills for artists and designers navigating the modern world. With the rise of digital art tools, colour exploration has expanded beyond

pigments to include screen-based simulations. Software like Adobe Photoshop and CorelDRAW offer digital colour spaces that require theoretical grounding for accurate reproduction. Pedagogical adaptation to these tools has become crucial for modern art training.

Conclusion

Bridging the gap between theoretical colour understanding and practical application requires an integrative, experiential, and cross-disciplinary pedagogical approach. This study underscores that learning colour effectively demands simultaneous engagement with cognitive, sensory, and creative processes. Through proper alignment of theory with studio experimentation, art educators can cultivate holistic colour literacy that transcends disciplinary boundaries.

Recommendation

- i. Art curricula should incorporate cross-disciplinary studio modules linking painting, graphics, and printmaking through shared colour projects.
- ii. Digital colour education should be embedded within traditional theory courses for students in painting and graphics specializations.
- iii. Reflective critique practices should be encouraged among the students as part of studio assessment.
- iv. Continuous professional development should be provided for art educators in contemporary colour pedagogy.

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